

Sultan Abdul Hamid II and the Arab states of the Ottoman Empire (1876-1908)

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Abstract

The research dealt with the conditions of the Ottoman state after Sultan Abdul Hamid II assumed power and his policy in managing the state and declaring the constitution, the situation of the Arab countries of the Ottoman Empire and the position of the Sultan towards it, as well as the manifestations of Arab national consciousness through the emergence of many associations, magazines and newspapers calling for equality, freedom and independence after the end of the rule Sultan Abdul Hamid and recognizing the federations, and recognition of the Arabic language an official language in the Arab countries of the Ottoman Empire.

Introduction

The conditions of the Ottoman Empire were disturbed and worsened remarkably in the second half of the nineteenth century, when the greedy foreign countries collided with it, and had it not been for the clash of interests of these countries in dividing the property of the Ottoman Empire, its deadline would have ended early. Many men and youth of the state were alerted to this fact, so they decided to put an end to these bad conditions that their country is going through, and accordingly they decided to depose Sultan Abdul Aziz, and in light of the force and the orchestrated coup, what they wanted was done for them, and they set the position of his brother Murad, who was sick, and soon For a long time, the disease became more severe, which forced a group of senior men of the state to remove it.

Medhat Pasha and his companions decided to take the covenants on the new sultan before pledging allegiance to him, so they decided to install Abd al-Hamid Effendi as a sultan on the condition of several conditions, as follows:

- 1- To announce the constitution immediately.
- 2- He should not consult in the affairs of the state except his responsible counselors.
- 3- To appoint known men who came to him to be his companions.

The Sultan answered their demands, and promised them more than them, and to expand the constitutional system, and said that he would abdicate the throne as soon as his brother Murad recovered from his illness.

Thus, Sultan Abdul Hamid II reached the Ottoman throne on the first of September 1876 AD, On the day of oath of allegiance, a large party was held, attended by ministers, consuls, statesmen and notables, and when they pledged allegiance to them, saying: I thank you for your congratulations, and I do not desire anything other than the progress of our kingdom and the comfort of our parishioners, and you will see from our deeds that support our promises of reform and that our subjects have to offer from the other side what they owe.

The status of the Ottoman Empire after the accession of Sultan Abdul Hamid

When Sultan Abdul Hamid came to authority, the Ottoman Empire was passing through a dark road and bad conditions, in addition to the Russian threats to the state by military intervention and war in defense of the peoples of the Balkans, as Europe showed its hostility to the state, especially after the atrocities committed in Bulgaria, as the state treasury was empty. Its budget suffers from deficit and inflation. This required setting up a plan for comprehensive reform in the state's policy and general conditions in order for it to reach the ranks of the developed country.

Sultan Abdul Hamid and the declaration of the constitution:

Sultan Abdul Hamid II began his reign by announcing the constitution on (August 31, 1876 AD) on the basis of merging the different races and sects into one melting pot, which impeded the continuation of constitutional life for a long time, and it seems that the Sultan did not announce the constitution out of loyalty and loyalty to those

who installed it. On the throne, and to those who promised them constitutional life, he soon became impatient with the parliamentary life, and as a result the opposition appeared in the council of the two envoys, and it was led by an elite of Arab representatives and some Turkish and Armenian representatives, and the Arab opposition was not here to defend the rights of Arabs. It was crystallized after but was in defense of the interest of the Ottoman Empire in general.

Sultan Abdul Hamid found in Russia's declaration of war on the Ottoman Empire, and the advance of its armies to Astana, a favorable opportunity to disrupt the constitution, in February 1877 CE, as the parliament meeting was postponed until 1908 CE.

The constitution drafted by Sultan Abdul Hamid was short-lived for several considerations, including: Medhat Pasha tried to establish a constitutional system for the empire without prior constitutional traditions, therefore, we do not see a strong reaction from the public opinion following the dissolution of Sultan Abdul Hamid to the Council of the two envoys, due to the loss of the conscious public opinion that has the duty to entrust the constitutional life, this is in addition to the foreign state's conspiracies and some reactionary elements aimed at undermining the foundations of constitutional rule.

After Sultan Abdul Hamid suspended work on the constitution, he imposed on his people - and gradually - an autocratic rule that affected all the components of the Ottoman Empire.

It was not unique to one sect without another. Sultan Abdul Hamid did not advocate racism and the Turkish policy, and did not promote the idea of Turkish nationalism, as did the federalists after him.

Sultan Abdul Hamid's policy of state administration:

Sultan Abdul Hamid relied in his policy on elements and groups that were not satisfied with the trends and ideas adopted by the free people, and he walked in his policy the path of absolute centralization in government, and through this he tried to fuse the various elements of the state into one melting pot, which raised vigilance among those elements.

This is at a time when the sultan started his reign with a bad start in terms of preserving the Arab-African states. In 1881 AD, France seized Tunisia, and in the second year Britain occupied Egypt and Sudan.

Thus, we notice the decline of Ottoman rule in North Africa, and by the end of 1882 AD, most of the state's states were lost in that region, so that only the states of Western Tripoli and Benghazi remained, which were also lost by the Ottoman Empire in 1911 AD, following the Italian invasion of them.

When the matter of the Ottoman Empire reached this point of shrinking, disintegration and dissolution, Sultan Abdul Hamid resorted to confronting the critical situation inside and outside the country to lay the foundations for his Islamic policy, as he wanted to harness religion in the face of his enemies abroad, to resist his opponents at home, and to strengthen his influence and control as the successor of the Muslims.

Sultan Abdul Hamid succeeded in achieving his goal after he adopted the idea of the Islamic university, as he was able to gain loyalty to the throne by appealing to the feelings of millions of Muslims from the Ottoman state and from outside it, and thus he was able to lead these Muslims, which would increase the strength of his position at the level. Foreign affairs, as well as consolidating his country's rule at home.

Perhaps the inhabitants of that region adhered to their freedom, in addition to the distance, and the difficulty of the transportation routes leading to it, among the most important obstacles that prevented the establishment and continuation of Ottoman rule there. As for the Arab-African countries under the rule of Sultan Abdul Hamid, it consisted of Egypt, Sudan, Western Tripoli and Benghazi, while Algeria had been under French control since 1830 AD

The policy of Sultan Abdul Hamid was directed towards the Arab countries, aiming to win over the Arabs like other Muslims. When the seeds of national awareness began to appear among the Arabs - especially the educated ones - the Sultan spent and poured money and gifts on Arab educational institutes, and he reformed the mosques of Mecca and Medina and Jerusalem, as it bestowed upon Arab leaders and their elders' appearances of honor and placed them in many high positions and at the same time chose a number of Arab soldiers to be part of his private guard. Many Arabs were favored by Sultan Abdul Hamid, what they were envious of.

On the other hand, however, the Sultan was concerned about the unrest that was occurring in the Arab countries, especially in Lebanon, and the emergence of revolutionary publications in Beirut, not to mention his fears that the Arabs were seeking to establish an Arab succession, which made him resort to violence and - sometimes - from some excuses justified his punishment of some sheikhs or leaders who did not implement his desires, and sometimes he forced some of them to reside in Istanbul, allow them a decent life, and at the same time surround them with spies and eyes to watch them, and he also sent his heresies to Arab countries, in order to sow discord and the causes of disagreement between the leaders Arabs and their tribes

It is noticeable that the Arab policy of Sultan Abdul Hamid was different and contradictory, including intimidation and enticement, and it was not without suspicion and suspicions of trust in most cases, especially after the emergence of the Beirut secret publications, which prompted the Sultan to tighten his control over the Arab countries, and connect it to a network of telegraph wire, then reinforce it with iron lines

Perhaps Sultan Abdul Hamid was aware of your country, and their country provides the state with the largest share of resources since their country, and the separation of the Arabs - who numbered about ten million souls -

means the collapse and fall of it, because their country provides the state with the most abundant resources. It also provides its army with a large pilgrimage of men

Perhaps the idea of the Islamic University adopted by Sultan Abdul Hamid was one of the most prominent methods in which he tried to attract Arabs in particular and Muslims in general, in addition to that this idea strengthened the stance of the outside and won him the loyalty of Muslims around the world as the successor of Muslims.

As for the Muslim Arabs in the Ottoman Empire, the thinking at first was different for them, as a large part of their common people were content to live under the state as long as it was Islamic, and there is another group of intellectuals who believed that the caliphate was for the Arabs, and that it extracted from them coercion after the takeover of the Ottoman Sultan Selim of Egypt. Therefore, the truth must return to its companions, and one of the most famous supporters of this idea was Abd al-Rahman al-Kawakibi

A third group saw that the state would be satisfied with comprehensive reforms undertaken by the state, without altering the administrative situation of the Arab countries, while a fourth team saw that the Arab countries in the Ottoman Empire should be granted broad authority in managing their affairs on their own, which is known as (decentralization). As for the remaining few, they were thinking about the necessity for the Arab countries to separate from the Ottoman Empire completely, and to establish an independent Western state. Whatever the case, the policy of despotism practiced by Sultan Abdul Hamid led to the emergence of many Arab secret groups and societies that were mostly calling for reform and salvation from absolute rule. The nineteenth century blocs were characterized by spontaneity that expressed a natural sense of national wish, but within Ottoman frame.

Despite these Arab groupings and blocs, they did not declare their national goals, but they succeeded - to some extent - in forming Arab forces bearing the seed of Arab nationalism that had the largest role in modern Arab history.

As a result of the cultural and media activity in the Levant, the growth of national awareness, and the increase in the number of Arab intellectuals, in the second half of the nineteenth century, these intellectuals composed a number of associations that adopted various principles and goals such as reviving old books, encouraging literature, and urging decent morals, to Other than the apparent goals and principles that associations adopt to cover their secret national goals. Undoubtedly, this matter is consistent with the historical conditions that the Arab nationalist movement is going through in that period. Among the most prominent of these associations were:

1- The Syrian Scientific Society (1857 AD).

The Syrian Scientific Society, based in Beirut, is the first secret Arab society whose membership reached (150) members, all of whom are educated Arabs. These members were both Muslims and Christians, scattered in various parts and cities of the Ottoman Empire, and what composes between them is their pride in the Arab heritage

This association was considered the cradle of a new political movement, and perhaps the first voice of the modern Arab national movement was with the first secret meeting held by the members of this association. And in which the poem of Ibrahim Al-Yazji was said, with the beginning of which:

"تنبهوا واستفيقوا أيها العرب لقد طغى السيل حتى غاصت الركب"

"Attention and wake up, Hey Arabs".

"The torrent was so overwhelmed that the knees sank"

It is the first poem that sang the glories of the Arabs and the glories of their literature and acknowledged the corruption of the ruling at that time, and it is the poem that called on all Arabs in the Levant to unite and work for the salvation of the Turkish rule. Thus, we can consider this poem or a hymn calling for political liberation in the Levant.

2- The Beirut Secret Society (1875 AD):

The first organized collective effort in the Arab national movement dates back to the year 1875 AD, when five young Christians formed a secret society in Beirut, known as the "Beirut Secret association".

Although it started with Christian members, it was soon joined by a number of Muslims, Druze and other sects, with the aim of confronting the Turks together, regardless of religion or belief.

When this association was calling for extremist goals and demands, it was not able to take advantage of the available publishing means at the time, and its activity was limited to issuing leaflets and posting them in the streets of Beirut, and these publications attacked the evils of Turkish rule and called on Arabs to revolt against it. In the year 1880 AD, three leaflets attributed to this association came out from Beirut, and the most important of these leaflets was the leaflet that was sent by the British Consul General a copy of it to his government on December 31, 1880 AD, and it included a record of the Society's political program, and it was one of the most important elements of this program

1- Recognition of the Arabic language as an official language in the Arab states.

2- Abolishing censorship and restrictions on free ideas and opinions.

3- The independence of Syria, united with Lebanon.

4- Using the forces recruited from the people of the country in military missions, within the borders of the region and not outside it.

The Astana government responded to these demands, by tightening control and broadcasting the eyes, which impeded the association's activities and led to its cessation before the end of 1883AD, when its members dispersed and most of them moved to Egypt

It seems that this movement did not produce noticeable activity among the residents who met it with a silent passivity, and perhaps its activity did not go beyond some Syrian cities, as for the majority of the residents of the Levant who were not aware of its activity, and it contributed to the confinement of these ideas, its extremism and its birth in an early, premature period.

3- As for the third association, it is the Association for Preserving the Rights of the Arab Community:

Which was established in the year 1881 AD and has published its appeal to the Arabs under the title "Statement of the Arab Nation", in which it called on them to pay attention to the oppression of the Turks towards them. And to work for the union and to claim their national rights

In Damascus, Sheikh Taher Al-Jazaery founded during his time there, **The association known as "The big Damascus Circle"** It included a group of educated, Gossip, and Arab thinkers, and it was calling for the education of modern sciences, the study of the history of the Arabs, their scientific heritage and the literature of their language, adherence to the advantages of religious morals, and the introduction of the benefits of Western civilization, as this association was in secret and close contact with the Young Turk Association, in order to seek from Inorder for the Arabs of the Ottoman Empire to obtain their rights within the Ottoman League

The Arab students in Astana also founded the "Arab Renaissance Society" and Moheb al-Din al-Khatib was elected as its president. This association was influenced by the views of Taher al-Jazaery, which he had broadcast in the Damascus episode the aforementioned.

In Aleppo, a group of its youth also composed an association called the "Polite upbringing Association" in 1907. This association adopted secret work in its activities, and it did not appear until after the constitution was announced in 1908, when many meetings were held in which its members called for the establishment of more associations to broadcast the spirit of scientific and literary sophistication

There is no doubt that what this assembly called for in its meetings were secondary and apparent principles, and it must have a national political character.

In Homs, a group of young people created, the "free Homs Association", with the intention of getting rid of the Ottoman administration in that region

It seems that these Arab societies spread until they prevailed in most of the cities and villages of Syria and Lebanon, and most of them were concealing behind the principles that demand the spread of education, the promotion of literature, the revival of old books, and other literary and scientific demands and goals.

In addition to these organized collective endeavors, we cannot fail to point out that there are individual endeavors exemplified by the actions of some free Arab men, such as Abdul Rahman Al-Kawakibi, author of "The Characteristics of Despotism and the Fights of Bondage" and his second book "Umm Al-Qura" and Najib Azouri, founder of the "Arab Nation League And other Arab scholars, reformers and politicians who awakened with their speeches and writings the potentials of pride in the souls, and reminded the sons of the nation of freedom and independence.

The Arab national movement began in the period between 1880 AD and the emergence of the Great Arab Revolt of 1916 AD, due to the control of Sultan Abdul Hamid and the severity of his wisdom, in addition to the result produced by the foreign penetration that followed the spread of Western education as missionary schools became a tool to achieve the political ambitions of states Colonialism, and colonial competition increased in the region, and the spread of Western education led to the emergence of an Arab literary renaissance accompanied by a political vigil that had the greatest impact on the growth and development of the Arab national movement

Newspapers and magazines and their role in the development of the Arab national movement

Among the matters that significantly contributed to the development of the Arab national movement was the emergence of many newspapers in the second half of the nineteenth century in many different regions of the Arab countries.

In 1855 AD, the newspaper (Adverbs) was published by its owner, Rizkallah Hassoun, and its rhetoric was against the Ottoman Empire, which caused its closure, nearly a year after its publication, and an attempt to arrest its owner who fled to Russia.

In 1858, (Al-Akhbar) newspaper appeared in Beirut, and in 1860, (Al-Jawa'ib) newspaper appeared in Istanbul, and a year later, the last newspaper (Al-Raid Al-Tunisi) appeared in 1865 A.D., the newspaper Syria appeared. In 1867 AD, "Al Furat" newspaper was published in Aleppo, and in the same year "Lebanon" newspaper followed "Al Zawra" newspaper in 1868

These newspapers, which were mostly semi-official, played a very important role in awakening the intellectual movement throughout the Ottoman Empire. As for the next stage in the emergence of a number of newspapers, it was at the beginning of the reign of Sultan Abdul Hamid II, where the newspaper (Al-Ahram) was published

in Alexandria in 1876 AD, and in 1883 AD. Zaman) It was published in Cairo, and the government closed it shortly after it was published. In 1888 AD, the newspaper (Al-Moqattam) was established After that, newspapers in the Arab country divided in their orientations, some of which had a pro-Ottoman accent, and some of them were loyal to the English, on the fact that in general they had a major role in the growth and development of the Arab national movement, and newspapers multiplied and multiplied, especially in the last quarter of the nineteenth century. And the efforts of the men of Syria who fled from the oppression and tyranny of Sultan Abdul Hamid combined with the efforts of their Arab brothers in Egypt, to raise the status of the press, which had the greatest impact in undermining the pillars of the Hamidite rule

Conclusion:

In sum, the Arab countries in the Hamidid era were full of scholars, reformers and politicians who awakened with their speeches, writings and articles the contents of pride in the Arab soul, and pushed the nation to understand the meanings of freedom and independence until one of the results of this intellectual movement was the establishment of many scientific societies, literary clubs, and the emergence of many Newspapers and magazines that were based on disseminating principles and ideas, and soon this situation developed into the formation of political parties, associations and clubs that aim to reform in the affairs of the state in general. Arab reformers also put in place many reform plans that they aim to preserve their existence and existence, and when the coup happened. Al-Dustoury in 1908 A.D. The Arabs were pleased with this, and they believed that the era of despotism had ended, so they joined the Turks in the belief that there was no difference in the state between its races, and they expressed their joy by announcing the establishment of the “Ottoman Arab Brotherhood Association”

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